

Comparative study of *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) and *Margosa Tree* (Neem) as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent in Diabetes mellitus type II

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Abstract:

In the current study, 60 obese and diabetic subjects between the ages of 35 and 55 were examined to determine the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of *Eugenia jambolana* Jamun pods and *Margosa Tree* Margosa Tree (Neem) seed powder. Both serum lipids and serum glucose were measured for each individual. The current study's findings suggest that the use of herbs is safe and beneficial in the early stages of type 2 diabetes, with *Jamun* being the best hypoglycemic agent when compared to *Margosa Tree* *Margosa Tree* (Neem).

Keyword: Diabetes mellitus type II, *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) and *Margosa Tree* Margosa Tree (Neem)) medicinal plants

1.Introduction:

Diabetes mellitus, also known as "Madhumeha," has been well-known for centuries and has turned into a global disease. A disruption of glucose homeostasis characterizes this chronic metabolic disease. Diabetes is a chronic, untreatable illness that affects practically all of the body's organs and systems. Several plants have proven helpful for people with diabetes. *Margosa Tree* (Neem) trees have many unique compounds that have been identified and others that are as yet unidentified, most analyzed compounds are-**Nimbin** (C₂₈H₄₀O₈) - Anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, anti-histaminic, anti-fungal, **Nimbidin** – Anti – tuberculous, anti-protozoal, anti-pyretic, **Gendering**- Vasodilator, anti-malarial, anti-fungal, **Sodium Nimbinat**e – Diuretic, spermicidal, anti-arthritic, **Quercetin** – anti-protozoal, **Salannin** – repellent and **Azadirachtin** – repellent, anti-feedant, anti-hormonal.(Siddiqui, 1945) & Santhoskumari, 1990, observed that Margosa Tree (Neem) leaf tea significantly reduces the need for insulin. Margosa Tree (Neem) leaf extract is a traditional herb for treating diabetes (Alam, et al., 1989) and has been scientifically proven effective in treating & preventing diabetes; (Murty, 1978); (Chakrabarty, 1984a). Oral doses of leaf extracts significantly reduced insulin requirements for non-insulin depended diabetes. (Pillai, 1981 b); (Luscombe, 1974); Murty (1978).

Aqueous extract of Margosa Tree (Neem) leaves significantly decreases blood sugar level and prevents adrenaline as well as glucose-induced hyperglycemia. (Murthy, K.S. et al 1978). The seed contains a glucoside jambolline ellagic acid, yellow essential oil, chlorophyll, resin, gallic acid and albumin etc. The bark has around 20% gum. It acts as an astringent and is used to cure skin disorder. The bark powder is sprinkled in bleeding disorder and wounds. Fruit pulp mixed with sesame oil is applied in burning sensations on the skin. Its fruit is an appetizer, digestive and liver stimulant. Impairment of liver function associated with diabetes is improved by seed powder. It is also an astringent. Leaves have anti-emetic property while bark is astringent. Excessive use of the fruit may cause constipation. The fruit and fruit juices are effective in disorders like loss of appetite, indigestion, pain and dysentery. its ethanolic extract shows hypoglycemic activities in albino rabbits. Later French scientists Sigogneau- Jagodzin-ski et al.1967, proved that constituents isolated from ethanolic extract had hypoglycemic action on alloxan induced diabetic rats (Sigogneau-Jagodzinski et al;1967). Ratsimamanga et al.1972, has reported ethanolic extract of bark of jamun tree has been used to decrease blood glucose level by 21% after one hour in hyperglycemic rabbits in a dose corresponding to 10g/ kg dry bark (Ratsimamanga et al.1972). According to (R. Bansal et al; 1981) oral feeding of seeds at 170, 240 and 510 mg/rat for 15 days, maximum reduction in blood glucose of normal fasted rats was observed at 240 mg/rat doses in comparison to chlorpropamide treatment. In addition, there was a 2.4-6.8-fold and 9.2-fold increase in cathepsin B activity pertaining to proteolytic conversion of proinsulin to insulin by seed extracts of *E. jabolana* and chlorpropamide respectively in rats (Bansal et al; 1981).

A Meta analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparation showed significant reduction of total serum cholesterol, in human subjects *Eugenia jabolana* (Jamun) purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides. It is one of those herbs which have favorable effect as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent. The main aim of this study was to see the effect of Garlic pods as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic in Diabetes melitus type 2.

2. Material and Method:

2.1 Experiment Place:

This study was conducted in Dept. of Biochemistry M.G.M. Medical College and Associated M.Y. Hospital Indore. And the subjects were selected from the outpatient Department of Medicine M Y Hospital Indore

2.2 Plant Collection:

All the plant components are bought from Ayurvedic shop Indore.

2.3 Inclusion Criteria:

Selection of subjects was done on basis of Blood Glucose not more than 180 mg/dl and HBA1C not more than 8mg%

2.4 Exclusion criteria:

History of any other clinical complication, taking any drug therapy Pregnant and lactating ladies.

Subjects were informed about the study in detail and consent was also taken before study.

2.5 Ethics Committee: The Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College approved the study.

2.6 Normal Healthy Control (n=50):

2.7 Study Subjects (n=200):

Estimations of the Biochemical parameters were done on study subjects then were compared with Healthy control.

2.8 Study subjects were divided into groups

i) *Margosa Tree (Neem) group (n=40) &*

ii) *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun) Group (n=40)*

2.9 Procedure:

A study was done to evaluate the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* pods and *Margosa Tree (Neem)* seed powder. Among the 60 obese and diabetic subject of 35 years to 55 years. 10 were taken as healthy control and 25 diabetic and obese were treated with *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* pods and 25 were treated with *Margosa Tree (Neem)* seed powder. The criteria of inclusion of study group in subjects was FBS > 110 mg/dl of glucose, >290 mg/dl of cholesterol, > 210 mg/dl of triglyceride, then 180 mg/dl of LDL. All the subjects were examined for serum glucose and serum lipids. *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun) & Margosa Tree (Neem)* seed powder 100mgs/day was given to the subjects of study group for 6 months and sample were collected at the starting day of study after two months, fourth and after six months of study for estimation of all parameters.

3. Results and Discussion

Table No. 01 Comparison between *Margosa Tree (Neem)* and *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* supplement groups after a period of two month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	NEEM Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	122.60±9.10	131.20±9.36	2.94	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	176.80±6.53	178.85±6.73	0.97	>0.05
CHOLESTROL	261.00±55.67	256.80±10.48	0.33	>0.05
TG mg/dl	107.0±3.65	105.8±5.16	0.84	>0.05
HDL mg/dl	37.50±2.94	45.6±2.28	9.72	<0.0001
LDL	63.05±5.30	60.90±3.43	1.52	>0.05
HBA1C mg%	7.730±.23	7.33±.23	5.35	<0.0001
UREA mg/dl	26.39±4.14	26.75±4.60	0.25	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.88±.08	.88±.093	0.19	>0.05
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.76±.39	3.96±.42	1.54	>0.05

Table no 1 after two months Fasting Blood Glucose, Serum HDL, HbA1c, is highly significant Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum LDL, Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine, Serum Uric Acid are found to be non-significant after oral supplements of herbs.

Table No.2 Comparison between *Margosa Tree (Neem)* and *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* supplement groups after a period of four month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	NEEM Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	95.40±9.62	108.25±11.47	3.83	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	152.95±14.05	139.95±8.76	3.51	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	248.50±10.33	243.10±7.77	1.86	<0.05

TG mg/dl	104.20±5.24	101.60±2.72	1.96	. <0.05
HDL mg/dl	37.10±3.75	49.70±4.23	9.96	<0.0001
LDL	58.30±4.55	54.05±4.34	3.01	. <0.0001
HBA1C	6.21±.41	6.21±.41	0.00	>0.05
UREA mg/dl	23.10±3.72	24.35±3.42	1.10	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.72±.090	.85±.10	4.41	<0.0001
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.88±.38	3.96±.45	0.63	>0.05

Table no 2 after four months- The results found after oral supplementation of herbs for four months are as follows: Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum HDL, Serum LDL are highly significant. Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides HbA1c along with Serum Urea, Serum Uric Acid is non-significant, while Serum Creatinine showed high significance (but within normal limits).

Table No. 3 Comparison between *Margosa Tree* (Neem) and *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) supplement groups after a period of six month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	NEEM Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	77.50±9.098	95.60±5.70	7.54	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	140.0±10.21	139.70±9.09	0.09	>0.05
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	241.85±5.45	233.15±4.34	5.58	<0.0001
TG mg/dl	106.30±4.11	100.35±4.97	4.11	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	40.25±2.93	60.05±5.13	14.9	<0.0001
LDL	56.10±4.37	51.90±3.78	3.24	<0.0001
HBA1C	4.97±.66	5.87±.66	4.30	<0.0001
UREA mg/dl	20.10±2.84	22.75±3.53	2.61	<0.01
CREATININE mg/dl	.63±.11	.84±.082	6.71	<0.0001
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.82±.45	3.73±.45	0.58	>0.05

Table no 3 after six months- The results were as follows: Fasting Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL, Serum LDL and HbA1c is found to be highly significant. Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Uric Acid is non-significant. Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine is significant (but within normal limits)

4. Conclusion:

Results of the current research Conclude that *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* is the best hypoglycemic agent in comparison to *Margosa Tree (Neem)*, and that herbal treatment is safe and efficient in the early stages of Diabetes mellitus type 2. The herb *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)*, which is a common choice for folk medicine and also has to be taken into consideration as a source for alternative medicine, is highlighted in the current studies as having the best hypoglycemic agent.

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